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Integrating FPGA-based Acceleration in Industrial Motion Control System

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ABSTRACT Manufacturing processes increasingly depend on advanced production machinery that must deliver high quality and large volumes. This applies to die-bonding machines as well that, especially at the time being after the years of shortage, need to meet very high standards of speed and accuracy. To achieve this, these devices are exploring the use of computer vision algorithms for automatic recognition of wafer positioning and die size. Nevertheless, these systems are typically managed by software-only solutions, which may fall short under stringent execution time requirements. A promising solution is the use of heterogeneous platforms, combining general-purpose processors with reconfigurable hardware. Such platforms offer the flexibility to handle both software tasks, which benefit from operating system support, and critical functions requiring hardware acceleration.

This paper presents a closed-loop implementation of a vision-based multi-sensor control system for an industrial application. The implementation exploits the capabilities of System on Module (SoM) technologies to provide flexible I/O and software execution coupled with computing acceleration for the vision algorithm on the reconfigurable Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) fabric. The FPGA coprocessor has been designed leveraging the High-Level Synthesis (HLS) technology and optimized on a dataset of 10k realistic images to meet the industrial use case’s performance, communication, and accuracy requirements. Moreover, the resulting accelerator performance and resource utilization demonstrate the possibility of reaching state-of-the-art metrics of handwritten hardware designs while allowing for higher abstraction and productivity of the design process.

INDEX TERMS Field Programmable Gate Arrays, High-Level Synthesis, Industrial Motion Control Systems, Multi-Processor Systems on Chip, Systems on Module.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. CONTEXT

In the realm of Industry 4.0, where manufacturing phases increasingly depend on intelligent production machinery, a pertinent case study is the wafer stage of a die-bonding machine [1]. Recently, we have experienced a severe chip shortage [2], and although the situation has eased, its future trend remains uncertain. Thus, improving chip fabrication is essential, and more efficient Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) can help achieve this goal. CPSs [3] have introduced numerous new application domains for advanced computation platforms at the edge, including industrial applications [4]. Within this context, the H2020 project IMOCO4.E [5] combines and leverages novel sensory information, model-based

approaches, and Industrial Internet-of-Things philosophies [6]. Its objective is to enhance mechatronic systems by making them smarter, more configurable, and more reliable while simultaneously boosting their performance. An IMOCO4.E’s Use Cases (UCs) focuses on improving the production rate of a modern die-bonding machine.

In this regard, [7] demonstrated that employing a multi-sensor approach, common in CPSs, and shifting advanced processing to the edge is strategically advantageous for enhancing the efficiency of industrial systems (like die-bonding machines). In that study, a multi-rate multi-sensor fusion algorithm was introduced to complement traditional systems, aiming to reduce operational errors that arise from inaccurate chip positioning. Typically, these systems utilize industrial

sensors (such as linear encoders) to provide feedback on the motor positions that move the machinery, but not on the positions at points of interest, which differ due to external disturbances. To address this issue, in [7], fast but noisy encoder measurements have been merged with accurate, delayed, and slow vision measurements, resulting in high-speed, accurate position estimates. This approach was demonstrated in a purely simulated environment and proved to improve the control system's closed-loop performance, at the condition that sufficient acceleration of the *Vision Algorithm (VA)* employed for the vision measurement is guaranteed.

A possible solution to accelerate the VA are the modern FPGA platforms offering comprehensive SoM support. SoMs incorporate all the core components of an embedded processing system (e.g., processor cores, communication interfaces, memory blocks, and hardware accelerators) in a single small board, easing the integration to application-specific peripherals (e.g., cameras). Due to their features, SoMs are becoming a popular solution for a wide range of industrial applications that require the use of i) their heterogeneous hardware components for flexible, yet accelerated, processing of different tasks and ii) their standard interfaces for handling communication protocols [8]. Indeed, FPGA-based platforms have been already utilized for implementing digital control in motion control systems and other Industry 4.0 application scenarios [9]–[11].

Regarding the target IMOCO4E die-positioning use, the feasibility of the acceleration through an FPGA has then been presented in [12]. There, the VA has been ported to FPGA through the use of HLS, paving the way towards the adoption of this kind of acceleration platform from Software (SW)-oriented developers. Indeed, high-level Hardware (HW) design SW tools, such as the HLS tools, do not require deep HW expertise and enable shorter time-to-market, often at the expense of lower efficiency than specialized Hardware Description Languages (HDLs). In addition, creating different versions of the same accelerator might, for example, require just a change of the HLS specifications in terms of previously defined parameters that impact conditional statements, avoiding lengthening design time due to implementation or manual modification of HW components.

B. OBJECTIVES AND CONTRIBUTIONS

This work aims at demonstrating the advantages of the proposed multi-sensor solution ported on an FPGA-based SoM, the AMD Kria K26 SoM, within a real-world industrial scenario. To fulfill this ambition, the some specific objectives have been identified.

- The VA has to be tested and validated on a dataset on real images, as in the previous works only synthetic images were considered.
- The coprocessor used to accelerate the VA has to be tuned with respect to dataset, as the algorithm presents some tunable parameters. The use of HLS design instead of tradition handwritten hardware makes this process feasible and efficient for SW-oriented developers.

- The full close-loop system has to be implemented to verify whether it meets the use case constraints. Such an implementation is made possible by the use of an advanced SoM that flexibly connects system's components.
- Demonstrating that the use of HLS for the design of the accelerator allows to reach SoA performance and efficiency compared to handwritten hardware solutions, which were not addressed in [12].

These objectives impose several advancements with respect to [7] and [12], which can be summarized in the following contributions:

- An extensive dataset of 10k images has been made available within project progress. This dataset captures typical conditions affecting die identification in realistic scenarios, such as the presence of nuances consequent to light and shadow effects, imperfectly straight edges resulting from the manufacturing process, and inclination of the wafer with respect to the conveyor belt axis.
- The selection of the optimal coprocessor configuration capable of fulfilling the requirements demanded by the use case. The assessment and selection process exploited the availability of the dataset. A Design Space Exploration (DSE) aimed at exploring the trade-off in terms of accuracy, execution times, and FPGA resources has been carried out.
- the integration of the proposed FPGA-based implementation into the system architecture, which matches the selected UC of the H2020 project IMOCO4.E. SoM potentials are exploited by managing via software the non-critical but time-constrained tasks that are the input acquisition from the camera and the output communication via ethernet. Moreover, proof that all the UC requirements, both in terms of computation and communication, are met is provided.
- The positioning of the proposed VA accelerator with respect to the state of the art. A detailed comparison between the chosen HLS-based coprocessor configuration and other HDL-based solutions present in literature, in terms of execution times and FPGA usage, shows how the proposed implementation offers a viable software-friendly alternative with respect to the state of the art.

The organization of this work is as follows. Section II outlines the background context of the UC (Section II-A) and the reference multi-rate multi-sensor system for industrial motion control [7] (Section II-B). Section III describes the setup related to the UC (Section III-A), the integration of the HW accelerator on the AMD Kria K26 SoM (Section III-B), and the HLS-oriented implementation of a VA (Section III-C). Section IV presents the results, which include: i) timing performance of the non-critical tasks executed onto the general-purpose processor of the AMD Kria K260V Vision Starter Kit (Section IV-C); ii) DSE exploring different configurations of the proposed HW accelerator with respect to a dataset of real input images (Section IV-A); iii) timing performance of

the chosen coprocessor in comparison to those of an Arm Central Processing Unit (CPU) (included in the AMD Kria K26 SoM) and a commercial x86 processor, and comparison with state-of-the-art implementations based on specialized HDLs (Section IV-D); iv) HW resource usage related to the chosen VA accelerator and other system components necessary for managing the acceleration, and discussion with respect to the state-of-the-art solutions directly designed with HDLs (Section IV-E); v) precision error in two different scenarios, each with varying parameters related to external disturbances and vision processing delays (Section IV-B). Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE INDUSTRIAL MOTION CONTROL

A. USE CASE (UC)

As previously mentioned, this work is in the context of the European project IMOCO4.E [5], and in particular concerns the UC related to semiconductor manufacturing [7]. Figure 1 (left part) shows the main components of the initial UC architecture from which this work started for the integration of the SoM into the closed-loop system. These components are briefly described below.

1) Host PC

A central host Personal Computer (PC) is essential for overseeing and coordinating the machine's operation. This host PC acts as the supervisory unit, responsible for initiating the machine's start-up and continuously monitoring the process flow and operational cycles. Key functions such as process control, feedforward control, vision processing, parameter setting and tuning are all managed by this central platform. Additionally, the host PC plays a critical role in machine status monitoring, predictive maintenance, and diagnostics, ensuring the efficient and reliable operation of the machine.

2) Motion Control Platform

Motion control platforms are essential for providing accurate and predictable feedback control at high sampling rates, typically within the kHz range [13]. These platforms can operate in either a centralized, decentralized or hybrid manner, allowing for the real-time monitoring of component states. Additionally, the motion control platform interfaces with analog/digital Input/Output (I/O) and encoders, manages multiple servo axes in advanced equipment, and executes Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) control.

3) Machine Hardware

The machine hardware consists of encoders, motors, physical components, and cameras. The I/O systems, motors, and encoders are handled by an embedded real-time motion controller. Encoders, which serve as sensors for tracking the position of the motor connected to the wafer table, can be sampled at different rates up to $20kHz$, depending on the desired precision for the application. Cameras, interfaced with the application processor, are focused on the wafer that contains an array of dies and should be selected to maintain

a high frame rate for the image stream in order to optimize real-time performance.

4) UC Requirements

With respect to the UC requirements (see Table 1), these involve timing and accuracy metrics. Since the die-cutting machine selected for the UC must achieve a minimum throughput of $60kunits/hour$, and potentially up to $100kunits/hour$ (equivalent to $36ms/unit$), timing requirements are directly tied to the machine's cycle time. In this regard, Figure 1 (right part) illustrates the task time sequence for each architectural components as expected during a machine cycle. The host PC is entrusted with all application tasks related to closed-loop system control. In this application, vision processing is the computationally most demanding task. Such a task executed as SW on general-purpose processors can take almost the entire time window required for a machine cycle (more than $30ms$ [14]). Once the next positioning of the motors is calculated, the motion control platform provides the signals to drive the actuators. The machine hardware consists of i) an encoder with a sampling frequency of $8kHz$ (corresponding to a time period of $125\mu s$), and ii) a camera with a high frame rate (e.g., $200fps$ corresponding to a time period of $5ms$), a region of interest of $88 \times 142 pixels$ and an accuracy of $3.5\mu m/pxel$. Nevertheless, accelerating the VA execution time to at least $1ms$ can decrease the error in die position [7].

On the other hand, to ensure correct die cutting, the maximum position error must be less than the machine assembly precision, which is at maximum $6\mu m$ [15].

Metric	Requirement
Throughput	$100kunits/hour$
Machine's Cycle Time	$36ms/unit$
VA Time	$1ms$
Position Error	$6\mu m$

Table 1: Overview of the UC requirements.

B. MULTI-RATE MULTI-SENSOR SYSTEM IN THE INDUSTRIAL MOTION CONTROL

Figure 2 shows the block diagram of a closed-loop control system that includes multi-rate multi-sensor fusion, VA, and control structure for industrial motion control application. All the details regarding the algorithms and the plant models are described in [7]. The application comprises various tasks (detailed in the following subsections) and aims to improve the positioning accuracy of industrial motion control systems at different control points and points of interest by integrating a VA system with a linear encoder. This integration effectively reduces errors caused by external factors that may affect the precise positioning of dies, which a linear measurement system alone cannot detect. A key finding of [7] is that the closed-loop performance of the control system, specifically in terms of Steady-State Error (SSE) (i.e., e_k at the end of each iteration), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) (equal to

one described below, processes camera images to ascertain the exact location of the object, including any disturbances, represented as $z_{v,k}$. Vision measurements are gathered at regular intervals of h_{vision} sample time, but image processing is computationally demanding. Consequently, the position information from the image captured at time-instance k , denoted as $img[k]$, becomes available after a delay of τ_v samples. A multi-rate multi-sensor fusion algorithm integrates data from both the linear encoder and vision measurements to compute the estimated position information used in determining the control action. Specifically, the work in [7] shows that reducing the vision sensor's sampling period (e.g. at least to $1ms$ with $h_{encoder} = 125\mu s$) decreases the error related to the die position.

4) Vision Algorithm (VA)

The VA is illustrated in Figure 3. This task is designed to compute the distance of the chip from the left edge of the containment plane. It uses an acquisition sensor to capture an RGB image, which is then converted to grayscale. To enhance the chip edges, a detection algorithm based on the Canny edge detector operator [17] is utilized. Subsequently, the Hough Transform (HT) [18] is applied to detect lines within the image, which can be adjusted to search for lines with specific orientations. In the given context, this approach leverages the fact that the camera views rectangular chips with linear edges. Furthermore, both the Edge Detection (ED) and HT processes were custom implemented for this UC. Specifically, the implementation focuses on identifying vertical edges in the input image and measuring their distance. Here are additional details on the implementation carried out in this paper:

- **RGB2Gray:** Since the conversion from RGB to grayscale depends on the resolution of the camera used for input acquisition, this step can be removed from the accelerated processing pipeline. Instead, it can be handled by a SW task that can adapt it to the resolution of the implemented accelerator, for example, by dividing the input image into slices to entrust them to multiple instances of the accelerator.
- **Edge Detection (ED):** The ED algorithm highlights the vertical edges of the image through the following four steps. First, the input image is convolved with a *Gaussian (GA)* filter to reduce noise from the environment where the image is captured. Next, the Sobel operator is applied to obtain two different gradients, task named *Gradient (GR)* in Figure 3, representing both the magnitude and direction of the edges. The following step, *Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS)*, calculates the gradient similarity to retain only the gradient with the highest magnitude value. Finally, the most significant edges are identified by applying a threshold function called *Hysteresis (H)*.
- **Hough Transform (HT):** This enables feature extraction of an image. Originally, such an algorithm was designed for detecting simple shapes like straight lines, circles, or

ellipses, but was later extended to identify the positions of arbitrary shapes. In the context of the proposed VA, the HT is applied to find vertical lines with slopes limited to a small range of angles. The algorithm processing involves three steps. First, *Hough Space Size (HSS)* transposes the image resulting from the edge detection into Hough space. Next, in a task called *Accumulation Point (AP)*, the number of lines that occur at each point in Hough space is examined, and if it exceeds a certain threshold, this identifies the position of vertical lines in a two-dimensional space called the Hough plane. Finally, the distances obtained in the Hough plane are converted into pixels corresponding to the identified lines, which can be plotted over the output image, and the distance to the edge of the image is calculated in the task named *Elaboration Data (EL)*.

III. TOWARDS A SOM-ORIENTED IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 5 illustrates the proposed architecture for the UC of the H2020 IMOCO4.E project. This setup includes: i) the die-bonding machine, ii) a silicon wafer transported by a conveyor belt which integrates motor and linear encoder, iii) a motion control platform connected to the die-bonding machine and the conveyor belt, iv) a host PC used for handling the plant, v) a camera for image acquisition, and vi) an edge device involving a processor-coprocessor system. Differently from that described in Section II (and illustrated in Figure 2), the host PC performs the application tasks except the ones associated with the VA, since the purpose is to separately accelerate their execution. For this reason, such tasks are handled by another computing platform, which can be placed at the edge (i.e., in close proximity to the plant). When data processing is required at the edge, the UC architecture leverages edge platforms, which are crucial for tasks like high-speed vision processing. High-speed vision algorithms can be deployed on embedded edge devices - such as embedded Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), FPGAs, and Application Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) - enabling applications in perception, localization, planning, and maintenance. These edge platforms can embed CPUs capable of running an Operating System (OS), which enables orchestration of containerized applications and software-based communication with a host PC. Additionally, these platforms function as smart sensors for higher control layers, processing input image data with high-performance computing capabilities under strict time-sensitive constraints. In particular, such devices can integrate a reconfigurable substrate in order to exploit HW acceleration. Nevertheless, the use of FPGAs is still not common in closed-loop systems of industrial controls, in which applications are typically specified as a software mapped onto general-purpose processors. Moreover, access from the FPGA to the various interfaces evaluates specific hardware implementations, which can be arduous to software developers. For these reasons, a potential solution that combines CPU, FPGA and easy-to-use peripherals is represented by the SoMs based on heterogeneous Multi-

Figure 3: VA pipeline [7] with the proposed HLS-oriented implementation.

Processor Systems on Chip (MPSoCs) (such as the AMD Kria K26 SoM provided with the AMD Kria KV260 Vision AI Starter Kit [19]). In addition, critical tasks to be deployed into the FPGA can be implemented by exploiting High-Level Synthesis (HLS), in order to favor a more software-oriented processor-coprocessor approach. Compared to HDL solutions, HLS increases the level of abstraction used to define a specific functionality, which can lead to increased design productivity at the cost of a loss in performance [20]. In addition, HLS typically provides the Intellectual Property (IP) generation of the accelerator in order to easily integrate it into the processor-coprocessor system. This integration leverages specific interfaces (for instance, based on AXI protocols), which, in the case of HDL implementations, must be handled by the designer. High-Level Synthesis (HLS) involves the compilation of high-level languages, such as SW programming languages, to FPGAs. This is crucial for the widespread adoption of FPGAs. HLS can also be understood as translating algorithmic descriptions into application-specific HW architectures. Most HLS tools utilize C or C++ for algorithmic specification, though other languages such as Python [21], MATLAB [22], or SystemC are also used. Nevertheless, each HLS tool limits the design choices related to hardware target (typically in terms of FPGA vendors) and specification language. Examples of C-based commercial HLS tools include Vitis HLS [23] (former Vivado HLS), Stratus HLS [24], Catapult HLS [25], SmartHLS [26] (former LegUp). These tools facilitate the compilation of C, C++, and/or SystemC code for FPGAs or ASICs and can be effectively integrated with other frameworks to provide system-level feature support [27]. The resulting HW accelerator can be optimized and customized using directives that instruct the compiler on specific desired features. The syntax and semantics of these directives vary by tool. Common directives (or *#pragma*) include pipelining and unrolling, which enable the HW to execute loop iterations in a pipeline or in parallel, as well as memory resources, interface, and partitioning, which allow for the customization of memory architecture and access. Additionally, commercial HLS tools generally provide support for performance estimation, design debugging, and verification. As an example of optimization through HLS, let consider a generic multi-task streaming functionality such as the one described in Listing 1, where each task ($T1$, $T2$, $T3$ and $T4$) is characterized by the iterative processing of specific functions (such as $f1$, $f2$ and $f3$). This functionality is structurally analogous to that to be accelerated (see Section II-B4). Typically, each task is optimized in order to decrease its impact in terms of either execution

time or hardware resources, or by choosing a balanced solution. Focusing on task $T1$ without optimizations, this would present circuitry and execution time as shown in Figure 4 (see the upper left portion). The addition of the *pragma pipeline* would lead to an increase in the number of registers to break the critical path, with a resulting gain in maximum frequency and interleaving of independent iterations within the task (see the lower left part of Figure 4). In the case where the latency requirement is more stringent than the hardware resource constraint, the use of unrolling would enable maximum parallelization of individual iterations only once the data are partitioned into independent memory blocks (see the central part of Figure 4). Since the unrolling requires multiple instantiation of hardware resources, its impact can be limited by minimizing the number of bits representing each data and the complexity of the involved functions (see the upper right portion of Figure 4). Once individual tasks are optimized, execution time can be reduced by pipelining tasks, at the cost of including buffers for passing data among tasks (see the lower right part of Figure 4).

```

1 void T1 (...) {
2   ...
3   for (i=0; i<3; i++) {
4     f1(a[i], b[i], x1, x2);
5     f2(x1, x2, y);
6     f3(y, c[i]);
7   }
8   ...
9 }
10 void T2 (...) { ... }
11 void T3 (...) { ... }
12 void T4 (...) { ... }
13
14 void top_module (...) {
15   ...
16   for (j=0; j<3; j++) {
17     T1 (...);
18     T2 (...);
19     T3 (...);
20     T4 (...);
21   }
22   ...
23 }
  
```

Listing 1: HLS code snippet of a generic task-based streaming functionality.

A. UC-LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION

Regarding the integration of the processor-coprocessor system with respect to the architecture envisioned for the UC application, this required the implementation of software functionalities for managing the acquisition of the input to be

Figure 4: Overview of the main HLS optimization techniques for a streaming functionality (as described in Listing 1).

Figure 5: Overview of the envisioned implementation for the UC application.

forwarded to the HW accelerator and the communication of the result of its processing to a host PC. The input images are captured using a camera connected to a USB port of the AMD Kria KV260 development board. These images can be then fed into the HW accelerator for processing. To handle the communication of the processed results from the HW accelerator, the implementation employs the HTTP protocol over ethernet. This strategy allows the processed data to be transmitted efficiently to a host PC. The host PC is responsible for further combining these results with other components within the closed-loop system, ensuring a cohesive and synchronized operation. This integrated approach not only enhances the performance of the system but also leverages the high-speed processing capabilities of the HW accelerator and the robust communication features of the HTTP protocol over Ethernet.

B. SOM-LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION

The processor-coprocessor system is implemented on an AMD Kria K26 SoM, which embeds a Zynq™ UltraScale+™ MPSoC [19]. The presence of such an

MPSoC makes it easier to adhere to the processor-coprocessor paradigm [28]. The MPSoC integrates a Processing System (PS) and Programmable Logic (PL) that communicate via dedicated interfaces. The PS includes a quad-core CPU (the sole processor used in this work), a dual-core Real-time Processing Unit (RPU), a GPU, an On-Chip Memory (OCM), a DDR controller, various interfaces (I/F) such as Ethernet and USB, several ports for the PS-PL I/F, internal interconnections, and additional modules such as a power manager and a safety and security module. Figure 6 shows the block design as depicted on Vivado Design Suite. In this context, the PS is represented by a specific IP (i.e., *Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC*). Except for this block associated with the PS, all the blocks in Figure 6 are part of the PL and constitute the coprocessor. Such coprocessor has been implemented primarily consisting of: i) an AXI-based bus for data and control communication between the processor and coprocessor (enabled with *AXI Interconnect* blocks); ii) a First-In First-Out queue (FIFO) for streaming data via the AXI-Stream protocol directly from the processor (*AXI-Stream FIFO*); iii) a Direct Memory Access (DMA) to

Figure 6: SoM-level block design on Vivado Design Suite.

facilitate AXI-Stream data transmission to the coprocessor while allowing the processor to continue executing other tasks (AXI DMA); and iv) the core of the coprocessor, which is the HW accelerator for the VA (VA IP). Note that although two modes of data transfer to the accelerator are available (via FIFO and DMA) for flexibility reasons (FIFO is faster for very small data because of the DMA overhead), the timing performance results (presented in Section IV) evaluate only the case where DMA is used.

C. IP-LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 7: Task execution of the VA IP.

The HW tasks of the VA (outlined in Section II-B4) have been implemented as an IP block. Within the VA IP, each HW task is defined as a submodule and optimized relative to its SW counterpart to comply with HLS guidelines. However, for optimization purposes, the *Non-Maximum Suppression* and *Hysteresis* tasks have been combined into a single block, while the *Hough Space Size* task has been split into two parts that can process either part or the entire input image (HSS^P and HSS , respectively). Table 2 provides a summary of the optimization techniques applied to each submodule. Pipelined registers have been introduced in each loop within the submodules to enhance throughput with minimal additional area overhead. Additionally, the choice to fully or partially unroll loops has decreased latency, though it has resulted in a significant increase in resource usage. Further timing optimizations involved using independent memory blocks to accelerate data access across nearly all tasks, with

the exceptions being *Accumulation Point* and *Elaboration Data*. Conversely, resource constraints have been addressed by carefully managing the size and type of data for all registers and memories, and by converting floating-point data to fixed-point data where necessary (e.g., $NMS\&H^P$, HSS^P , HSS , and EL). Additionally, the computational complexity of certain mathematical functions required for processing (such as sine, cosine, arctangent, and square root) has been managed using optimized versions from HLS libraries or by employing tabulated values. To minimize execution time and reduce resource usage (particularly memory blocks), tasks that can be executed on independent sections of the image (including edge detection tasks and HSS^P) are handled using pipelining and linear buffers.

Figure 7 illustrates the execution phases of the VA IP. The tasks in the pipeline process one pixel line of the input image at a time and are marked with P , while other tasks operate on the entire image and are executed only once per frame. Moreover, the amount of HSS and AP processing varies depending on the slope with respect to the vertical axis that can be evaluated for straight line identification. In particular, the range of angles has been defined through a configuration parameter called θ expressed in degrees, which leads to different VA IPs. As an example, Listing 2 refers to a code snippet of the task EL for a specific θ configuration, in which some optimization techniques are also applied. θ parameter affects the implementation in terms of resource usage due to the dependence of the variable val_div , which is equal to $(IMG_HEIGHT/2) * \sin(\theta)/\cos(\theta)$. Nevertheless, since val_div is required only for integer values of θ between $-\theta$ and $+\theta$, it can be defined as an array of size $2\theta + 1$ of fixed-point integers (with $24bits$ in total, and $4bits$ for the integer field). This strategy requires the use of 2 optimization techniques: sampling the equation in terms more suitable for HLS (removing divisions and sine and cosine functions) and converting the data type (from *float* to *ap_fixed*). The code snippet also gives examples of other HLS code optimization techniques: pipelining, unroll, and data sizing. Pipelining is

Type	Optimization Technique Description	HW Tasks						
		GAP	GRP	NMS&HP	HSSP	HSS	AP	EL
Pipelining	reduces the interval for a loop to process new input data	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Loop Unrolling	enables the parallel execution of independent loop iterations	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Array Partitioning	allows parallel memory access with smaller memory instances	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Data Sizing	optimizes the resources actually needed for data processing	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Data Type Conversion	decreases data handling resources without affecting precision	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
HLS-friendly Functions	optimize SW-oriented libraries for HW implementation	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Task Pipelining	improves task-level concurrency and overall design throughput	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Line Buffering	minimizes the resources required to pass data between tasks	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗

Table 2: Use of optimization techniques in the HW tasks. ✓ and ✗ indicate the use or non-use of the technique in the specific VA IP task, respectively.

applied via a *#pragma* directive, as is unrolling, which in this case was limited to a factor of 2 in order to not excessively increase the required FPGA resources. On the other hand, the data sizes were optimized by reducing the number of bits required by integer variables, with particular attention to the range of values that can be represented (signed and unsigned).

```

1 const ap_fixed<24,4,AP_RND> val_div[11] =
2 {-3.721949, 0.000000, -2.479412, 0.000000,
3 -1.239067, 0.000000, 1.239067, 0.000000,
4 2.479412, 0.000000, 3.721949};
5 ...
6 int16_t dataPeaks[MAX_PEAK_NUMBER]={0};
7 ap_fixed<24,4,AP_RND> theta;
8 ap_fixed<36,16,AP_RND> peak;
9
10 for(int8_t x=0;x<MAX_PEAK_NUMBER;x++) {
11 #pragma HLS UNROLL factor=2
12 #pragma HLS PIPELINE
13   theta=peakCoordinates[x+MAX_PEAK_NUMBER]
14     *0.01745;
15   int8_t the_int=(theta*100);
16   int8_t ind=the_int+5;
17   peak=peakCoordinates[x];
18   int16_t distance=peak-val_div[ind];
19
20   if(distance<0) distance=0;
21   else if(distance>(IMG_WIDTH-1))
22     distance=(IMG_WIDTH-1);
23
24   dataPeaks[x]=distance;
25 }
26 ...

```

Listing 2: HLS code snippet of the task EL, where pipelining, unrolling, data sizing, data type conversion and HLS-friendly functions are applied.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

First, this section reports two DSEs. The former has been performed to understand how changing the θ parameter in the VA IP could affect in terms of accuracy, execution time and FPGA resources (Section IV-A). Such a DSE enabled the identification of the most suitable configuration for the HW accelerator to be implemented with the complete FPGA design flow. The latter has been required to verify the importance of the VA acceleration in the multi-sensor multi-rate approach (Section IV-B).

In addition, this section shows how the fulfillment of the latency requirements given by the UC (Section IV-C) is achieved. In particular, the evaluation regards the non-critical tasks specified as a software and related to i) the acquisition of the input image by the AMD Kria K26 processor, ii) its subsequent RGB-to-grayscale conversion to be forwarded toward the coprocessor, and iii) the ethernet-based processor-to-host communication associated with the result of the vision algorithm accelerated in the coprocessor. Finally, the implementation selected in IV-A has been compared with the state of the art in terms of execution time (Section IV-D) and FPGA resource utilization (Section IV-E).

To evaluate the VA IP and its integration within a full processor-coprocessor environment, the Vitis HLS and Vivado Design Suite (version 2023.1) have been utilized.

The coprocessor, incorporating the integrated VA IP, was synthesized using the Vivado Design Suite at a maximum frequency of $230MHz$. Thus, all subsequent results are based on this reference frequency. Additionally, the VA IP has been tailored for the specific use-case scenario, which involves processing input images of size $88x142pixels$, with each pixel represented in grayscale format.

A. DSE: SOM

In [7] the HW accelerator had been evaluated with a synthetic input image, where the chip was represented as a square centered in a different colored background (see Figure 8a), no slope nor rotation to the vertical axis were considered. In this work, an assessment of the VA IP over a dataset of $10k$ real images (still having a size of $88x142pixels$) is performed to evaluate its performance and efficiency in identifying the position of the chip in the reference UC scenario. The real images provided as input have varying characteristics in terms of shape, inclination, nuances, and shadows. For example, in Figure 8b a realistic image¹ affected by shadowing effect is shown. Figures 8a and 8b show respectively how the identification of the die center is perfectly accurate in the synthetic image case and how it may deviate from the correct value (labelled in the reference dataset) in the real image case. In this regard, investigating how the θ parameter of the vision algorithm could impact accelerator processing turned

¹Real images cannot be included in the paper due to Non-Disclosure Agreements.

HW Configuration θ range[$^\circ$]	Error [μm] ([%])			Execution Times [μs]	PL Resource Usage [%]			
	μ	σ	max abs		FF	LUT	BRAM	DSP
± 2	2.02 (2.29)	1.41 (1.60)	8.17 (9.28)	35.67	6	20	0	3
± 3	1.79 (2.03)	1.27 (1.44)	5.49 (6.24)	37.98	6	22	0	3
± 4	1.98 (2.25)	1.37 (1.56)	7.48 (8.50)	43.54	7	24	0	3
± 5	1.98 (2.25)	1.38 (1.57)	9.35 (10.63)	47.03	7	26	2	4
± 8	2.01 (2.28)	1.57 (1.78)	7.80 (8.86)	59.39	8	31	2	5
± 12	2.01 (2.28)	1.57 (1.78)	7.80 (8.86)	77.84	9	38	3	6

Table 3: Comparison among different θ -dependent configurations of the proposed VA IP in term of estimation error (μ mean value, σ standard deviation, and $max\ abs$ maximum in absolute value) achieved with a dataset of 10k real input images. θ is a parameter corresponding to the range of angles representing the inclination of the chip in the input image evaluated for identification. Estimations extracted with Vitis HLS of execution times (@230MHz) and resources usage (related to the AMD Kria K26 SoM) for the VA IP are also reported.

Figure 8: Die position identification with the synthetic input image used in [12] and a real image (representation) as in the dataset used in this work.

out to be important. As already indicated in Section III-C, this parameter represents the range of angles with respect to the vertical axis in which the VA IP is capable of identifying straight lines present in the input image. Evidently, when the chip has a slope beyond the θ 's range, identification may be more difficult if not incorrect. Figure 9 depicts that, starting from the edge image, the identification of the die center may change due to the configuration of this HT parameter. In particular, wider ranges of θ are affected by erroneous identifications due to more inclined dies (see Figure 9a). Similarly, also sloping edges associated with manufacturing imperfections or shadows may lead the HT algorithm to erroneous solutions (see Figure 9b). Increasing theta also implies additional hardware resources and larger execution times, since it requires more computational complexity to examine the lines/edges with higher slopes. Specifically, θ

Figure 9: Die position identification with different values of the θ range parameter.

variations affect the processing of tasks HSS and AP , so that a value of θ -dependent clock cycles, $cc(\theta)$, should be considered. The mathematical are reported hereafter:

$$cc(\theta) = cc_{HSS}(\theta) + cc_{AP}(\theta) \quad (4)$$

$$cc_{HSS}(\theta) = \frac{N_\theta(\theta) \cdot N_\rho(\theta) \cdot IMG_{size,pad}}{uf_{HSS}} \quad (5)$$

$$cc_{AP}(\theta) = \frac{2 \cdot N_\theta(\theta) \cdot N_\rho(\theta)}{uf_{AP}} \quad (6)$$

$$N_\rho(\theta) = IMG_{width} \cdot \cos(max(\theta)) \quad (7)$$

$$N_\theta(\theta) = 2 \cdot \theta + 1 \quad (8)$$

$$IMG_{size,pad} = (IMG_{width} - 6) \cdot (IMG_{height} - 6) \quad (9)$$

where θ is expressed in degrees, $N_\theta(\theta)$ and $N_\rho(\theta)$ are the number of values considered in the Hough Space (ρ values for the y-axis and θ values for the x-axis), uf_{HSS} and uf_{AP} are the unrolling factors used in the HLS pragmas of the tasks *HSS* and *AP*, and $IMG_{size,pad}$, IMG_{width} and IMG_{height} represent size (excluding padding), width and height of the input image respectively. Please note that, given these relationships, the chosen unrolling factor affect not only the execution time but also the required hardware resources.

All these functional and non-functional considerations motivate the need for implementing different versions of the VA IP with varying θ before any closed-loop implementation. It must be noted that having adopted an HLS-based design paradigm, the whole DSE process was facilitated since all the configurations under scrutiny were automatically generated from the different high-level descriptions by tuning θ .

Table 3 highlights this tradeoff in selecting a specific VA IP configuration. In particular, the best accuracy has been obtained with $-3 \leq \theta \leq 3$, since the maximum absolute error is the only one lower than the machine assembly precision ($6\mu m$, see Section II-A). Although the average error is also reasonably small for other HW configurations, this is higher for $-2 \leq \theta \leq 2$ (due to shadowing effect) and, starting from $-4 \leq \theta \leq 4$ (due mostly to chip rotations effects), grows as θ increases until saturation is reached. Regarding execution times, as expected, an increase with θ is observed. Nonetheless, no critical values are to be reported since all the configurations allow to meet the timing requirement of $1ms$.

With respect to the HW resources, the percentage of usage on the target FPGA remains limited to low values, except for the Look-Up Tables (LUTs), which increase as θ varies, reaching up to almost doubling from the smallest to the largest θ (but increasing by only 2% in cases evaluated with low θ s).

In summary, the best hardware configuration corresponds to the one with $-3 \leq \theta \leq 3$. It is the most accurate, with a very small penalty in execution time (+6.5%) and FPGA resource utilization (+10% of LUTs, corresponding to +2% with respect to the total) compared to the most efficient case, which is the one with $-2 \leq \theta \leq 2$. Therefore, this value of θ has been chosen to implement the VA IP embedded in the coprocessor, for which the results are presented in the following sections. Please note that, although in the considered scenario all the identified accuracy and processing requirements are met with a simple edge detector, from a purely algorithmic perspective, DSE results could improve with the application of different edge detectors. Their use could, in principle, lead to a more straightforward linear relationship between θ and accuracy. Such algorithmic optimization though goes beyond the scope of this paper.

Scenario 1: $\Delta_1 = 20$, $\Delta_2 = 15$, $\Delta_3 = 10$, $\Delta_4 = 5$, and $\Delta_5 = 0$.							
$h_{encoder}$ [ms]	h_{vision} [ms]		Die position				
			1	2	3	4	5
0.125	0.125	SSE [μm]	0.138	0.162	0.208	0.11	0.0312
		MAE [μm]	0.826	1.216	1.362	0.364	0.022
		ST [ms]	25.32	29.43	24.38	27.44	29.51
0.125	0.25	SSE [μm]	0.200	0.280	0.326	0.191	0.0501
		MAE [μm]	1.164	1.620	1.836	0.232	0.035
		ST [ms]	18.62	25.34	30.43	25.73	20.49
0.125	0.5	SSE [μm]	0.431	0.331	0.418	0.112	0.151
		MAE [μm]	2.724	2.913	2.663	1.960	0.086
		ST [ms]	19.32	23.52	30.11	28.12	23.16

Table 4: Closed-loop performance of multi-rate sensor fusion in the Scenario 1. All the deviations (Δ_i), where $i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ for 5 dies are in μm .

Scenario 2: $\Delta_1 = 40$, $\Delta_2 = 20$, $\Delta_3 = 10$, $\Delta_4 = 5$, and $\Delta_5 = 0$.							
$h_{encoder}$ [ms]	h_{vision} [ms]		Die position				
			1	2	3	4	5
0.125	0.125	SSE [μm]	0.246	0.283	0.220	0.186	0.065
		MAE [μm]	0.932	1.463	1.530	0.364	0.030
		ST [ms]	27.11	30.43	26.72	29.31	31.47
0.125	0.25	SSE [μm]	0.259	1.910	0.511	0.231	0.091
		MAE [μm]	1.466	1.814	2.313	1.112	0.070
		ST [ms]	19.47	32.40	33.61	28.60	23.73
0.125	0.5	SSE [μm]	0.611	0.530	0.502	0.311	0.220
		MAE [μm]	3.180	3.412	3.120	1.170	0.090
		ST [ms]	24.30	27.33	20.01	33.28	29.61

Table 5: Closed-loop performance of multi-rate sensor fusion in the Scenario 2. All the deviations (Δ_i), where $i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ for 5 dies are in μm .

B. DSE: CLOSED-LOOP SYSTEM

To assess the effectiveness of the closed-loop control system that integrates the multi-rate multi-sensor fusion II-B3 and utilizes ED and HT II-B4 as a VA, a DSE across different parameters and scenarios has been conducted. This evaluation targets high-precision industrial motion control applications, such as pick-and-place operations in semiconductor manufacturing. As detailed in [7], Tables 4 and 5 illustrate the performance of the closed-loop control system in terms of Steady-State Error (SSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Settling Time (ST).

In the pick-and-place task, ideally, five semiconductor dies are sequentially positioned with consistent spacing. The camera's region of interest is centered on the first die at $z_0 = 0\mu m$. The objective is to align the first die with a target position of $220\mu m$ by the end of the first iteration. In a different scenario where external disturbances impact the die position, the linear encoder sensor, which only monitors the position of the wafer table, cannot detect the inaccuracies. However, the vision sensor, utilizing captured images and a VA, can precisely determine the actual position of the die.

Tables 4 and 5 illustrate two different scenarios. In the first scenario, an initial disturbance of $\Delta = 20\mu m$ is applied to the first semiconductor die, followed by disturbances to dies two, three, and four, with each subsequent disturbance decreasing by $5\mu m$. The fifth semiconductor die remains unaffected. In the second scenario, an initial disturbance of $\Delta = 40\mu m$ is applied to the first die, and disturbances to dies two, three, and four decrease by a factor of 2. The fifth die experiences no disturbance. In these scenarios, the linear encoder operates with a sampling period of $h_{\text{encoder}} = 0.125ms$, while the VA is tested with sampling periods of $h_{\text{vision}} = 0.125ms, 0.25ms, 0.5ms$. The performance results for both scenarios are shown in Tables 4 and 5. Generally, the SSE values are below $1\mu m$ in most cases, though they vary depending on the disturbances. Performance metrics such as SSE, MAE, and ST tend to worsen when $h_{\text{vision}} = 0.5ms$ compared to the case with $h_{\text{vision}} = 0.125ms$. Thus, minimizing vision delay and using a shorter h_{vision} is advantageous, and the proposed accelerator’s execution time can accommodate these sampling requirements.

C. PROCESSOR EXECUTION TIME EVALUATION

Since the UC application is composed of sequential SW tasks without any parallelism, its response time is the sum of the execution times of each task, which represents its critical path [29]. Table 6 summarizes latency contributions of the SW tasks executed $10k$ times and mapped onto the PS of the Kria K26 (SW-1), which features a quad-core Arm® Cortex®-A53 MPCore™ running up to $1.5GHz$. Results show how the total execution time (also called response time) meets the requirements mentioned in Section II-A4 also with the addition of the accelerator latency (reported in Section IV-A). Note that these run times are based on the SW implementation only. Nevertheless, a dependency will then be placed on the frame-per-second capability of the camera employed. Effectively, the minimum sampling period for the acquisition of a new frame (e.g., $5ms$ with $200fps$) will need to be added. Therefore, in order to meet the requirement of maximum sampling every ms , high-speed cameras need to be employed [30]. On the other hand, the latency results also disregard the time required to transfer the output of the coprocessor in the local network (from the Kria KV260 to the host PC), which is in the order of a tenth of a millisecond in the implemented setup.

The combined use of software tasks (running on the CPU) and hardware (implemented in FPGA) requires data transfer from the PS to the PL of the MPSoC. In the specific use case, this transfer is influenced by the drivers used to manage the AXI DMA. The execution times for this transfer have been measured, with maximum values of $81\mu s$ for the configuration and $69\mu s$ for transferring the entire image to the coprocessor. Nevertheless, the configuration only needs to be set once during device initialization (rather than being managed for each frame), and the data transfer time to the accelerator is partially overlapped with the processing time related to the VA IP, since the processing is pipelined by

handling one line of the image at a time. Specifically, it does not overlap only with the tasks not involved in the pipeline (HSS, AP, and EL), which in aggregate have an execution time of $4.07\mu s$ out of the total $37.37\mu s$. For these reasons, the maximum execution time for data transfer via AXI DMA can be effectively considered equal to $35.7\mu s$. Finally, the transfer time for reading the output from the VA IP register is almost negligible (in the order of microseconds).

Task	Execution Times [μs]			
	SW-1 (on Arm Cortex-A53)			
	μ	σ	min	max
Image Capture	280.00	13.58	260.00	400.00
RGB2Gray	110.00	5.80	100.00	170.00
Position Sending	80.00	26.77	50.00	250.00

Table 6: Execution time evaluation (μ mean value, σ standard deviation, *min* minimum value, and *max* maximum value) of the SW tasks.

D. COPROCESSOR EXECUTION TIME EVALUATION

Figure 10: Comparison among HW and SW versions of the VA IP in terms of mean execution time (on the left) and HW speed-up compared to the SW-1 and SW-2 values (on the right).

Figure 10 illustrates a comparison between software and hardware versions in terms of mean execution time. The SW results were obtained from $10k$ runs of the VA SW IP

performed on: i) the PS of the Kria K26 (SW-1, as done in Section IV-C); and ii) a 6-core AMD Ryzen 5 5600 processor, which operates up to $4.4GHz$ (SW-2). For a fair comparison, the execution of the VA was conducted using a single core for the software cases (SW-1 and SW-2) and one accelerator for the hardware case (HW), with both being assessed at their maximum operating frequencies. All processing steps involved in the Edge Detection and the Hough Transform, as detailed in Section II-B4, were accelerated, leading to an overall speed-up of 24.89x and 18.20x compared to SW-1 and SW-2, respectively. This significant acceleration meets the constraints outlined in Section II-A4 and [7] for the VA to effectively support the MSF of the industrial motion control system depicted in Figure 2, thereby enabling scenarios with improved precision error (see Section IV-B). In contrast, the software executions evaluated (SW-1 and SW-2) may not fulfill the required time constraints (since their maximum values are $1.02ms$ and $1.28ms$ respectively). This discrepancy arises because the speedup values are disproportionately favorable towards the proposed hardware implementation, particularly for tasks that are executed multiple times per frame (i.e., pipeline tasks). Although higher operating frequencies of CPUs can result in speedups closer to 1 (or even lower in one case, i.e. for the ED task) for tasks that are more characteristic of general-purpose implementations. Nonetheless, the designed VA IP completes its tasks in $37.37\mu s$, well below the required $1ms$, even when accounting for processor-coprocessor communication overhead, including the latency associated with the DMA transferring the image to the coprocessing unit. In fact, thanks to the acceleration to $37\mu s$ of the set of VA hardware tasks, and by summing the measured maximum execution times of the software tasks shown in Table 6 (which results in $820\mu s$) and the combined tasks related to the input/output data transfer (which is about $36\mu s$), the requirement reported in Table 1 remains satisfied (since $893\mu s < 1ms$).

E. COPROCESSOR RESOURCE USAGE EVALUATION

Regarding resource usage, the coprocessor utilizes a small portion of PL resources, primarily allocated to the VA IP (refer to Figure 11), although it has been designed through HLS. Resources required for VA IP submodules associated with ED and HT are also reported. The results reflect the optimizations applied to the original software code (as outlined in Table 2). Specifically, the 16.48% usage of LUTs is largely due to loop unrolling, which increases the number of hardware blocks needed for parallel processing. Additionally, the extensive use of the pipeline directive contributes to the 7.60% utilization of Flip Flop (FF) registers. Even though the accelerator processes the input image one pixel line at a time, it requires 4 blocks of $36kb$ Random Access Memory (RAM), which is 2.78% of the total Block Random Access Memory (BRAM) available on the target FPGA. The need for only 1.76% of Digital Signal Processors (DSPs) resources is attributed to typical image processing operations in the tasks *GR* and *HSS*. Besides the resources for VA IP, the coproces-

Figure 11: PL resource usage of ED, HT, VA IP and the whole coprocessor (@ $230MHz$) in terms of FF, LUT, BRAM and DSP of the AMD Kria K26 SoM.

sor contains additional resources are used for DMA, FIFO, and components managing clock, reset, and interconnect functions (for more details see Figure 6). Despite this, the VA IP allows for the integration of additional functionalities on the coprocessing unit (such as the MSF discussed in Section II-B3) or for the deployment of multiple instances of the VA IP. This last case represents a scenario in which multiple accelerators can be deployed in case i) part of the proposed VA IP is to be reused, or ii) the same VA IP is to be used to process larger inputs without implying additional execution time than those presented in Section IV-D.

F. HLS-BASED COPROCESSOR VS HANDWRITTEN HDL-BASED SOLUTIONS

This section proposes a comparison between the HLS-based implementation of the accelerator presented and solutions in the literature based on handwritten HDL. In particular, the comparison regards the two state-of-the-art algorithms (i.e., Edge Detection and Hough Transform), which are combined in the VA IP. To the authors' knowledge, no other works using the same HLS tool and SoM can be involved for a direct comparison. Therefore, the proposed comparison focuses on the same type of adaptive technology, the FPGA, but includes different vendors' platforms, such as AMD (formerly Xilinx) and Intel (formerly Altera), in the implementation of handwritten HDL solutions.

In terms of content, Tables 7 and 8 extend those presented in survey papers [31] and [32], which were respectively related to Edge Detection and Hough Transform. In addition, to allow a more fair comparison of implementations on FPGA-based platforms belonging to different device families and produced by different vendors, two metrics have been used for normalization of FPGA execution time and resource usage: time per pixel ($ns/pixel$) and resources per pixel ($slices/pixel$). The normalized execution time ($ns/pixel$) has already been used to directly compare efficiency relative to image size in [31], [32]. Whereas, we are introducing the normalized resource usage, which is represented in terms of slices. The conversion in terms slices starting from a memory block can be derived by each Look-Up Table (LUT) with the following formula 2^{in} , where in is the LUT input size (i.e.,

6-input LUT corresponds to $2^6 = 64\text{bit}$ memory block), and by the knowledge that each slice contains a different number of LUT (lut_s), e.g. the AMD Kria K26 contains 8 6-input LUTs, while the implementation in [33] is adopting a 7-input LUT. To the slices already considered in [31] and [32] (s), those derived from the corresponding memory blocks expressed in $bits$ (b_{mem}) have been added to obtain the total used resources (res_{tot}) using the following formula:

$$res_{tot} = s + \left(\frac{b_{mem}}{2^{in} \cdot lut_s} \right) \quad (10)$$

As an example, considering the total resources of this work given in Table 7, the Equation 10 becomes $res_{tot} = 20,925[\text{slice}] + \left(\frac{18 \cdot 1000 \cdot 8[\text{unit}]}{2^6 \cdot 8[\text{unit}/\text{slice}]} \right) = 21,206[\text{slice}]$.

Numerically speaking, in terms of normalized execution time, the proposed implementation of the ED achieves $2.50\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$, which is more efficient than [34] ($24.80\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$) and [31] ($4.69\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$), and closely aligns with the performance of [35] ($2.17\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$). However, it falls short compared to the highly efficient methods of [36] ($0.57\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$) and [37] ($0.50\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$). With respect to the HT, the proposed solution achieves a normalized execution time of $2.85\text{ns}/\text{pixel}$, which is the most efficient among all methods. In this regard, it should be highlighted that the implementation involved in the VA IP is limited to the detection of straight lines with a small slope from the vertical axis (-3 to $+3$ degrees), while the other approaches in the literature include more extensive functionalities. In summary, with respect to the normalized execution time, the proposed HLS-based implementation of the ED and the HT are aligned with the handwritten HDL ones present in the state of the art, proving the suitability of the chosen approach for possible real-time applications where processing speed is critical.

Regarding the FPGA resources, the proposed ED implementation utilizes the AMD Kria K26 FPGA, with $20,925\text{slices}$ and 18kB of memory blocks. This configuration seems more resource-efficient in terms of memory usage compared to [35] (192kB), [36] ($16,184\text{kB}$), [37] (278kB), and [31] (261kB). Such efficiency related to the memory blocks is achieved at the cost of a superior usage of slices, but still in line with the works oriented to reduce memory resources: [36] ($23,904\text{slices}$) and [37] ($17,928\text{slices}$). For the HT implementations, the proposed work utilizes $16,196\text{slices}$ and no memory blocks of the AMD Kria K26 FPGA. As mentioned above, since the proposed implementation is more limited in terms of functionalities, it does not require the use of memory blocks, making it extremely memory-efficient compared to all other methods: [38] (381.5kB), [33] (200.5kB), [39] (105kB), [40] (828kB), and [32] (203.1kB). Nevertheless, the absence of memory blocks led to an increment of slice usage. In particular, focusing on the normalized resource usage, all the handwritten HDL solutions achieve better efficiency. In summary, with respect to normalized resource usage, the proposed implementations for both the ED and the HT fall shorter in terms of resource usage with respect to the more optimized handwritten HDL

ones. Overall, the resource efficiency result was expected. HLS-based solutions generally improve design productivity at the cost of reduced efficiency. Nonetheless, in this particular case, it does not affect the final result, since the normalized execution time is comparable, or even superior, to the more optimized handwritten state-of-the-art solutions, allowing real-time execution, while meeting the UC requirement in term of acceleration.

V. CONCLUSION

This work provides additional support for the benefits of using heterogeneous platforms that integrate general-purpose processing with programmable logic to address the needs of modern industrial motion control systems. Specifically, the main goal was to showcase how enhancing system performance in terms of die-cutting machine throughput and die identification capability, as specified by the H2020 project IMOCO4.E, can be achieved by accelerating the VA block. This improvement is made possible through the use of a coprocessing unit, which allows for the integration of a comprehensive vision-based control system on the same computing platform. Performance results indicate that the proposed SoM-based solution meets the timing requirements of the UC. This has been achieved thanks to two DSEs focused on i) assessing accuracy of the VA IP through a dataset of real input images and ii) improving precision error of the closed-loop system providing the proper acceleration of the VA. In addition, to encourage software developers in the industrial sector to consider this implementation approach, two strategies were employed. The strategy involves using the AMD Kria KV260 target device, which is designed for advanced vision applications and eliminates the need for extensive hardware design expertise. Although it is a “non-production” version not intended for final commercial deployment, the AMD K26 family of this SoM also includes a production model with additional connectors, an eMMC non-volatile memory (allowing the system to boot entirely from the SoM rather than an SD card), and a wider temperature range. This production version supports a complete operating system to manage software execution and facilitate I/O. The development process began with a software-friendly implementation and progressed to a hardware-oriented version using HLS. The final VA IP achieves the state-of-the-art performance both in terms of execution time and resource usage. The HLS-based design provides an easier path to hardware acceleration for developers, allowing them to progressively focus on various types of optimization. In addition, HLS enabled the accuracy-related DSE to be performed more rapidly, since it simplified the implementation of different accelerator configurations.

Further works aimed at improving die position identification could evaluate parametric accelerators based on AI models or exploit the GPU embedded into the SoM for SW-oriented implementations.

Metrics	[34]	[35]	[36]	[37]	[31]	This Work
Image Size [<i>pixel</i>]	360x280	512x512	512x512	512x512	512x512	88x142
Frequency [<i>MHz</i>]	27	292	250	272	56.7	230
Execution Time [<i>ms/frame</i>]	2.50	0.57	0.15	0.13	1.23	31.18E-3
Norm. Execution Time [<i>ns/pixel</i>]	24.80	2.17	0.57	0.50	4.69	2.50
FPGA-based Platform	Altera Cyclone	Xilinx Virtex-5	Xilinx Virtex-5	Xilinx Virtex-5	Altera/Intel Cyclone IV	AMD Kria K26
LUT per Slice [<i>unit/slice</i>]	1	8	8	8	1	8
LUT Input Size [<i>unit</i>]	4	6	6	6	4	6
Slices [<i>slice</i>]	-	4,553	23,904	17,928	3303	20,925
Memory Blocks [<i>kB</i>]	-	192	16,184	278	261	18
Total Used Resources [<i>slice</i>]	-	7,553	276,779	22,272	133,803	21,206
Norm. Resource Usage [<i>slice/pixel</i>]	-	0.03	1.06	0.08	0.51	1.70

Table 7: Comparison of execution times and FPGA resources between the proposed submodule for the Edge Detection and the related state-of-the-art implementations.

Metrics	[38]	[33]	[39]	[40]	[32]	This Work
Image Size [<i>pixel</i>]	1024x768	1024x768	752x320	1000x1000	640x480	88x142
Frequency [<i>MHz</i>]	200	200	40	260	200	230
Execution Time [<i>ms/frame</i>]	15.59	5.4	13.92	3.86	1.47	35.56E-3
Norm. Execution Time [<i>ns/pixel</i>]	19.80	6.8	57.84	3.86	4.78	2.85
FPGA-based Platform	Altera Cyclone IV	Altera Stratix IV	Xilinx Spartan 3A	Xilinx Virtex VII	AMD Virtex-5	AMD Kria K26
LUT per Slice [<i>unit/slice</i>]	1	1	2	8	8	8
LUT Input Size [<i>unit</i>]	4	7	4	6	6	6
Slices [<i>slice</i>]	29,431	4,115	3,692	82,673	1,119	16,196
Memory Block [<i>kB</i>]	381.5	200.5	105	828	203.1	0
Total Used Resources [<i>slice</i>]	220,181	16,646	29,942	95,611	4,292	16,196
Norm. Resource Usage [<i>slice/pixel</i>]	0.28	0.02	0.12	0.10	0.01	1.30

Table 8: Comparison of execution times and FPGA resources between the proposed submodule for the Hough Transform and the related state-of-the-art implementations.

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